

Zybertspheres - Core Gravity

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In Zybert Cosmology the universe comprises Zybertspheres, \textcircled{Z} . Ours has an antineutron core, enveloped by a matter-antimatter creation zone, enveloped by a growing expanding spherical neutron cloud. Core gravity, \textcircled{a} , is all pervasive affecting all matter and antimatter and light. \textcircled{a} acts radially from \textcircled{Z} centres along the Axis of Zybert and manifests as \textcircled{G} and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$.

The anomalous orbital precessions, planetary flybys, Pioneer 10 and galactic V vs R profiles are natural \textcircled{Z} phenomena in Zybert Cosmology, where \textcircled{a} is manifested as $\textcircled{G}v$ and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$. Thus, the Newton Gravitational Constant G is superseded by the Zybert Gravitational Variable \textcircled{G} , which is a composite variable of local predominance, along with $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ of cosmic predominance. $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda = \textcircled{a} * \text{Cos}(\phi) * \text{Cos}(\theta)$ and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda * R$ is an attractive gravitational acceleration caused by \textcircled{a} .

In the Milky Way $\textcircled{G}M/R^2$ and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda * R$ ($\textcircled{a} * \text{Cos}(\phi) * \text{Cos}(\theta) * R$) have equal acceleration at ~ 12 kpc. \textcircled{G} and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ cause flatter V vs R profiles but outer rotation is dominated by $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ over \textcircled{G} [1]. Whereas with GPS, EMR \hat{c} is little affected by $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ in that short distance [1].

\textcircled{Z} are anisotropic therefore so is \textcircled{G} . \textcircled{G} is a composite parameter of a constant part $\textcircled{G}c$ and a variable part $\textcircled{G}v$ where $\textcircled{G} = \textcircled{G}c + \textcircled{G}v * \text{Cos}(\phi) * \text{Cos}(\theta)$, ϕ is the angle to the Axis of Zybert and θ is orbital angular position, and has a lesser effect.

Simulations of the following phenomena [1] showed

P10	$\textcircled{G} = 6.674300000532006E-11$	$(6.6743e-11 + 5.32006e-21)$ and
Precession	$\textcircled{G} = 6.674305480600000E-11$	$(6.6743e-11 + 5.48060e-17)$ and
Galileo flyby	$\textcircled{G} = 6.674326274000000E-11$	$(6.6743e-11 + 2.62740e-16)$ where
with the P10 trajectory on a plane $\sim 6^\circ$ to the ecliptic plane, the Galileo flyby trajectory $\sim 37^\circ$, planetary orbits nearly coplanar and an Axis of Zybert $\sim 84^\circ$, the angles of those planes to the Axis of Zybert, give $\textcircled{G}v$, when $\textcircled{G}v * \text{Cos}(0) = 5.0e-16$ and an average $\text{Cos}(\theta) = 1$, as		
	ϕ	$\text{Cos}(\phi)$
P10	89.9993902	$1.0640e-5$
Precession	83.7071	$1.0961e-1$
Galileo flyby	58.29	$5.2559e-1$
		$\textcircled{G}v = 5.0e-16 * \text{Cos}(\phi)$
		5.32006e-21 [1]
		5.48060e-17 [1]
		2.62740e-16 [1].

This would make the Axis of Zybert in close alignment with the Axis of Evil, not surprising since the Axis of Zybert creates anisotropy and the Axis of Evil reflects anisotropy.

$\textcircled{G}c$ and $\textcircled{G}v$ are omnidirectional, but in our visible sphere, a tiny speck in the stelliferous zone of our \textcircled{Z} far from the \textcircled{Z} centre, $\textcircled{G}v$ is effectively unidirectional along the Axis of Zybert which makes \textcircled{G} anisotropic and variable through $\textcircled{G}v$.

\textcircled{a} manifests as \textcircled{G}_v and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ both of which are anisotropic, and as $\textcircled{G}_v \propto 1/r^2$ and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda^*r \propto r$, \textcircled{G}_v predominates locally and $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ predominates cosmically, as

- an omnidirectional anisotropic $\textcircled{G} = \textcircled{G}_c + \textcircled{G}_v$ and
- a unidirectional $\textcircled{Z}\Lambda$ as a component of \textcircled{a}' at ϕ to the Axis of Zybert creating \textcircled{Z} phenomena such as
- $\delta\theta$ in precession of planetary orbits,
- δv in spacecraft flybys,
- δa of blue shifted EMR from spacecraft as measured on earth,
- δc of EMR from orbiting satellites
- anisotropic Doppler shifts of measured cosmic light,
- anisotropic measurements of expansion rates,
- a variable anisotropic Gravitational parameter,
- flatter V vs R profiles of galaxies and
- curved light paths.

[1] Zybetspheres - Phenomena.xlsx see <https://zenodo.org/records/17034092>